

A Study on Impact of Quality of Work Life on Job Satisfaction of Self Financing College Teachers in Dindigul District

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Abstract

Quality of work life significantly contributes towards increasing the job satisfaction or dissatisfaction depending upon the Teachers negative or positive perception of quality of work life dimension. Teachers indicated positive job satisfaction and would continue to stay in the same job only if they have opportunity for growth and development along with organizational prestige and financial factors. The main objectives of the study are to examine the effectiveness of teachers in achieving their quality of work life in their job, to know the impact of job satisfaction on quality of work life among the self financing college teachers and gives the suitable suggestions on the basis of the study. The study population comprised the self financing college teachers of Dindigul District. By using proportionate random sampling method 120 women teachers were considered as final sample for the study. In this study it is founded that there is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and quality of work life of women teacher. Also the study reveals that working environment has more impact on the quality of work life than pay and job security aspects.

Introduction

Teachers role is pivotal in providing education, creating knowledge, facilitate technological advancement and enriching the national culture. The concept of work life is based on the assumption that a job is more than just a job. This value based process is aimed towards meeting the twin goals of enhanced effectiveness of educational institution and improved quality of life at work for teachers, it is concerned with increasing teachers and managements cooperative to solve the problems of Improving institution performance and teachers satisfaction. Quality of work life and quality of life has a significant association in teaching environment. Quality of academicians, particularly in the private technical institute, is not in a better condition. Factors such as salary and wages biasness for growth is low salary and job security issues are badly affecting the relationship with administration and academicians, dissatisfaction regarding leave

flexibility etc, are responsible for low quality of work life of respondents. Teaching effectiveness is important because effective teaching helps students learning and improve the quality of work life of teachers.

Statement of the Problem

The study is reference to the impact of quality of work and job satisfaction self financing college teachers in Dindigul district. The self financing college teachers have realized that quality of work life improves employee motivation, job performance and institution growth but some of the factors influence the quality of work life are individual employee’s wages, working hours, work place condition, and fairness in the work place personal characteristics such as anxiety or depression.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the effectiveness of teachers in achieving their quality of work life in their job.
- To know the impact of job satisfaction on quality of work life among the self financing college teachers.
- To give the suggestions on the basis of the findings of the study.

Review of Literature

The study analyzed on the College Teachers revealed that, there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and QWL dimensions. They founded that QWL of college teachers, particularly in the Private Technical and Professional Institute is not in a better condition. There is a huge difference between salary and job security of the same qualified teachers of private aided and unaided institutes. [1]. The study stated that there is a positive significant relationship between job satisfaction and quality of work life of women teacher. Also the study reveals that working environment has more impact on the quality of work life than pay and job security aspects. So educational institutions need to concentrate more on better working conditions to increase the quality of work life of working women teachers [2]. The study regards to the results of hypotheses and theoretical and experimental studies, they analyzed the hypotheses and discussed their comparisons with the literatures.[3].

Sampling Technique

By using proportionate random sampling method 120 women teachers were considered as final sample for the study. The data was collected from the sample respondents through survey method by administering questionnaire developed for the purpose.

Analysis and Interpretation

Basis		No. of respondents	Percentage
Age Group	20-25	11	9.2
	26-35 years	107	89.0
	36-45 years	2	1.8
	Total	120	100
Gender	Male	27	22.5
	Female	93	77.5
	Total	120	100

Marital Status	Married	84	70
	Unmarried	36	30
	Total	120	100
Qualification	PG	14	11.7
	M.PHIL	100	83.3
	PhD	6	5.0
	Total	120	100
Income	Upto Rs.8000	113	94.2
	Rs.11,000-20,000	6	5
	Above 20,000	1	0.8
	Total	120	100

The above table reveals that more than half of the respondents (89%) come under the age group of 26-35years and 9.2% of the respondents belong to the age group of 20- 25years and Only 1.8% of the respondents were in the age group of 36-45years and below. It is understood from the table given above that vast majority of (89%) of self financing college teachers were in the middle age. To analyze the hypothesis whether “there is no significant relationship between age of the respondents and quality of work life on job satisfaction of college teachers”. The analysis of variance was applied and the result shown in the following table.

	Sum of square	d.f	Mean square	F	Sig
Between group (combined)	0.134	2	0.642	0.642	0.528
Within group	12.191	117	0.104		
	12.325	119			

The table reiterate (77%) of respondents are female whereas (22.5%) of respondents are male. A best part of the respondents (77%) are female respondent. To analyze further whether “there is no significant relationship between gender of the respondents and impact of quality of work life on job satisfaction. The analysis of variance was applied and the result shown in the following table.

	Sum of square	d.f	Mean square	F	Sig
Between group (combined)	0.965	2	0.483	2.829	0.063
Within group	19.960	117	0.171		
	20.925	119			

The table interprets (70%) respondents are married and at the level of quality of work life on job satisfaction whereas (30%) of respondents are unmarried to analyze furthermore hypothesis is framed that “there is a no significant relationship between marital status of respondents and quality of work life on job satisfaction of respondents” the analysis are made through analysis of variance and the results are shown below.

	Sum of square	d.f	Mean square	F	Sig
Between group (combined)	0.179	2	0.090	0.419	0.659
Within group	25.021	117	0.214		
	25.200	119			

It is also evident from the table that (83.3%) of respondents where completed M.Phil and they have a medium level of quality of work life on job satisfaction and (11.7%) respondents who are post graduates and (5%) of respondents are Ph.D. Most of the respondents are M.phil graduates.

Their level of quality of work life towards job satisfaction “ there is no significant relationship between educational qualification of the respondents and the level of quality of work life towards job satisfaction of respondents the results are shown below

	Sum of square	d.f	Mean square	F	Sig
Between group (combined)	0.633	2	0.317	1.968	0.144
Within group	18.83	117	0.161		
	19.467	119			

The above table also indicates that (94.2%) of respondents are earning below Rs.6000 and (5%) of respondents are earning Rs.6000-Rs10000 and (0.8%) of respondent earning above 20000 hypothesis is framed for further analysis that “there is a no significant relationship between income of the respondents and quality of work life toward job satisfaction of respondents”.

Findings of the Study

- The major findings of the study stated that the Respondents belonging to the age group of above 26-35years have a high level of quality of work life on job satisfaction than other two groups .
- Respondents of female have a high level of quality of work life on job satisfaction when comparing to male respondents.
- Respondents with M.Phil qualification have a high level of quality of work life on job satisfaction than with the qualification of P.G and Ph.D.
- Respondents earnings Rs. 8000 having high level of significant.
- The analysis of variance shows the result that there is no significant relationship between age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, income and quality of work life on job satisfaction of respondents.

Suggestion

- The study suggested that Faculty members play a significant role for economic growth by contributing their knowledge, skills and efforts. So in Self financing colleges the management should emphasize on the policy implications based on the concerned issues of Quality of Work Life improvement.
- To encourage the faculty members, they should use motivational factors such as, providing compensation and salary, adequate conditions for work, perfect appreciation of their work; develop a sense of belonging and collaboration to do duty, sympathetic understanding etc. These should be considered as satisfying motivators of their job.
- The government should also take a measure to improve the quality of work life and job satisfaction by reducing the turnover rate of self financing college teachers.

Conclusion

Based on the above discussion it is concluded that, the study reveals that working environment has more impact on the quality of work life on job satisfaction. If college teachers are happy with the factors such as attention paid to their opinion, responsibility, recognition, and attention paid to their suggestions, they experience better quality of work life. So educational institutions need

to concentrate more on better working conditions to increase the quality of work life of teachers. The present study was limited to the population of the self financing college teachers in Dindigul District only. Hence, the generality of the results may not represent the entire college teachers across the all over state or country.

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